

ALG. J MAT CHEM

Green synthesis of reduced graphene oxide using orange extract for Ni²⁺ removal

Amarachi Udoka Nkwoada^{1*}, Austin Dominic Terna¹, Christopher Ikpeamadi Nwoko¹

¹Federal University of Technology Owerri, School of Physical Sciences Department of Chemistry, PMB 1526, Nigeria

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received: 07 January 2021

Revised form: 27 March 2021

Accepted: 09 April 2021

Keywords :

Reduced graphene oxide,

Orange extract,

Thermal decomposition,

Nickel (II) ions,

Characterization.

ABSTRACT

Green synthesis of reduced graphene oxides provides cost-effective, readily available, and improved material properties. Orange extract-assisted reduced graphene oxide was synthesized by thermal decomposition. The material denoted as o-rGO was characterized via XRD, SEM and FTIR Spectroscopy. Findings confirmed synthesis of o-rGO was successful with interlayer spacing of 2.98 Å and crystallite spacing of 0.54 nm on the material surface. The adsorption performance of o-rGO was investigated over concentrations of Ni²⁺ in aqueous solution, pH, temperature, and contact time. Removal efficiency of Ni²⁺ by o-rGO was 97 % in 10 mins. Equilibrium adsorption data fitted well into Tempkin isotherm, while Intra-particle diffusion was the rate-determining step. Adsorption kinetics was elucidated by pseudo 1st order model. Thermodynamic parameters demonstrated that the adsorption process was endothermic and non-spontaneous. The findings highlighted the effective green synthesis of reduced graphene oxide for the removal of Ni²⁺ ions in aqueous solution. In addition, o-rGO potential for sensors, supercapacitors, and photocatalytic applications can be exploited.

© 2021. All rights reserved

Introduction

Many concerned researchers specializing in reduced graphene oxide have continued to publish advances of this wonder material over the years with reported adsorption and materials applications [1- 4]. The Reduced graphene oxide has honey comb like cage structures, with various functional groups, which makes it an efficient adsorbent for removal of metals in aqueous solution. Authors have also reported on the efficient removal of Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺, and Pb²⁺ by reduced graphene oxide owing to their reactive polar functional groups like -COOH, -OH and -NH₂ [5-7].

Hence, reduced graphene oxide is applied in the removal of heavy metal contamination in certain industrial

* Corresponding author: Amarachi Udoka Nkwoada

E-mail address: chemistryfrontiers@gmail.com

applications. A typical application of reduced graphene oxide increases the petroleum oil capacity of the composite foam when added to natural rubber [8]. Additionally, functionalized reduced graphene oxide shows remarkable properties such as supercapacitance and sensor applications [9, 10]. Among the preparation techniques is the use of organic extract synthesis for improved adsorption performance. For instance, *Citrus sinensis* peel studies showed significant removal of Cu^{2+} metal than wood sawdust [11]. Similar work on the selective removal of five different heavy metals using modified orange peel showed that orange peel functions well in binary systems as efficient adsorbents [12]. In addition, the green synthesis of reduced graphene oxide is a potential material in the removal of dye from wastewater [13]. Interestingly, when reduced graphene oxide adsorbents are enhanced with algal extracts, high adsorption capacity of 93 mg/g and 82 mg/g for Cu and Pb metals were achieved [14]. Also green synthesis of reduced graphene oxide adsorbents using strawberry extracts, showed significant improvement for supercapacitors and photocatalytic applications [15].

However, structural defect is also a significant challenge in the synthesis of reduced graphene oxide due to interference with the reaction system. Nevertheless, it is known that a well reduced graphene oxide material has large surface area and improved crystallinity [16]. The synthesis can be achieved via thermal heating that improves crystallinity and low defect. Comparably, researchers have used thermal reduction technique to synthesis grape–assisted reduced graphene oxide and the adsorbent improved in adsorption capacity for the removal of organic dye [17]. In this sense, citrus seeds, pulp, peel, and residues were reported to find applications in functional materials and energy materials [18]. Additionally, orange peel extracts are known to form organic protective layers over surfaces by means of a physical adsorption process [19]. This interaction is associated with R-COO- functional groups on the surface by physisorption [20]. Interestingly, *Citrus Sinensis Linn* has not been applied in the synthesis of reduced graphene oxide to the best of our knowledge. Hence, this research work will investigate orange extract synthesis of reduced graphene oxide for the improved removal of Ni^{2+} in aqueous solution.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Preparation of Orange Extract

Local indigenous Oranges (*Citrus Sinensis Linn*) were collected from a farm land near Federal University of Technology Owerri. One of the oranges was repeatedly washed with tap water to remove sand and dust impurities from its surface. Afterwards, it was cut open and the seedlings removed. About 40 g of the whole orange (without the seeds) was crushed in a blender and transferred into a round bottom flask containing 50 mL de-ionized water. The mixture was heated for 20 mins in a water bath and allowed to equilibrate at room temperature. After that, the colored solution was filtered to obtain the extract [17].

2.2 Preparation of Graphene Oxide (GO) and Reduced Graphene Oxide

They analytical grade reagents used were KMnO_4 , H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 , NH_3 and graphite selected for the adsorption experiments and purchased from Fischer Scientific Nigeria Limited. They were utilized without any further

purification. 3 g of graphite, 18 g of KMnO_4 Wt. equivalent and 360/40 mL of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$ were carefully reacted together with continuous stirring as described in previous research in Ref 4. The mixture was filtered to get graphene oxide and the filtrate washed with deionised water to a pH of 7.0. To prepare the orange assisted reduced graphene oxide (o-rGO), 90 mg of GO was added into 140 mL extract and stirred briskly to disperse the GO uniformly in the extract. 400 μl aqueous NH_3 was added into the reaction mixture changing the color. The reaction blend was maintained between 318–323 K in a water condenser at different time intervals of 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 hrs. After completion of these heating cycles, the o-rGO was filtered and dried at constant temperature of 353 K to obtain about [17]. This process was repeated in triplicate to obtain a weighed o-rGO sample of about 500 mg.

2.3 Batch Adsorption Experiments

Ni^{2+} standard solution used in the adsorption experiment was carefully prepared from NiCl_2 to obtain a concentration of 40 mg/L. Throughout the batch adsorption experiment, only the specific parameter being analyzed was varied at predetermined intervals, while every other parameter was kept constant (temperature was 273 K, pH at 7.0, Ni^{2+} solution was 50 mL, mass was 20 mg and concentrations at 40 mg/L, while contact time was 10 mins). The centrifuge and magnetic stirrer were operated at 10,000 rpm and 170 rpm at 10 mins interval between them. Measured amounts of adsorbents (adsorbent concentration: 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 mg/L) were added into 50 mL Ni^{2+} for the adsorption analyses. Furthermore, the effect of adsorption time (Contact time: 2, 5, 10, 20, 30 mins), effect of pH (5, 6, 7, 8, 9) and Temperature (303, 315 and 328 K) was investigated to determine the optimal adsorption constraints and factors using the formula:

$$q_e = \frac{v(C_0 - C_e)}{m} \quad (1)$$

The q_e (mg/g) is the adsorption capacity of Ni^{2+} ions for the o-rGO; V (mL) is the specific volume of used standard solutions prepared. C_0 (mg/L) and C_e (mg/L) are the initial and the equilibrium concentrations of the Ni^{2+} ions while m (g) is the adsorbent dosage [21-22].

2.4 Characterization

The Scanning electron microscope (SEM) micro structural characterization of the o-rGO samples was done using JSM-6400 JOEL having an acceleration voltage of 29.5 kV and Current 29.9 mA. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was achieved via Equinox 300 model with $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ radiation (1.54059 Å) at voltage of 40 kV and a 50 mA current. The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were obtained using Perkin Elmer 8790 model instruments. Samples of o-rGO were compressed with KBR into thin pellets and the concentration of heavy metals analyzed by Atomic absorption spectroscopy model AA 500 Pg [22-23].

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Material Characterization

The SEM images for GO and o-rGO is presented in figure 1 (a) and (b) respectively. The morphological

appearance of o-rGO was essentially smaller than GO and will consequently provide additional reactive sites for adsorption. On the other hand, GO by virtue of its large size supports less reactive sites. Also, the large size of GO indicated the presence of coarse particles while o-rGO was finely distributed after thermal reduction.

Fig. 1 SEM images for (a) GO and (b) o-rGO

In addition, the o-rGO sheets suggest a closely packed array of sheets, while GO depicted broad layered sheets. These observations were likewise noted by some researchers in their work for development of reduced graphene oxide for sensors, supercapacitors and photocatalytic applications [10, 15]. Also, Songsaeng et al [8] remarked that the ordered arrangements of GO, and o-rGO similarly shows cell structures of various pore sizes resulting from thermal reduction of GO to o-rGO material

XRD images of GO and o-rGO is depicted in Fig. 2 showing the diffraction angles. The GO was diffracted to the left while o-rGO was diffracted to the right. There was a strong peak at $2\theta = 8.5^\circ$ for GO, corresponding to GO (001) crystal face with interlayer spacing of $10.2 \text{ \AA}$ and 0.18 nm crystallite size. A broad and impressive peak at $2\theta = 28.5^\circ$ corresponding to o-rGO crystal face (211) with interlayer spacing of $2.98 \text{ \AA}$ and crystallite spacing of 0.54 nm based on theoretical calculations [5]. They correspond to the intercalation of functional groups containing oxygen and arising from thermal reduction of GO to o-rGO. Additionally, the crystallite size of synthesized GO and o-rGO were in nanoscale and point towards promising functionalization and applications.

The results also indicated that graphite was successfully oxidized to form GO. Furthermore, the GO was effectively reduced to o-rGO with the orange extract that enhanced the thermal reduction process. These results are consistent with observations from previously published research works [14, 24-25].

FTIR spectra of GO and o-rGO are shown in Fig. 3. The GO had peaks at 3541 cm^{-1} and 3354 cm^{-1} . They produced a very steep and prominent intense broad band which indicated presence of hydroxyl moieties like epoxy, hydroxyl, carbonyl and carboxylic in graphene oxide. They other peaks at 2113, 1999, 1623 and 1039 cm^{-1} and 877 cm^{-1} indicated C-O stretching. C-OH stretching and C=C stretching vibrations disappeared in o-rGO

and strongly indicated that there was formation of reduced graphene oxide. The peak around 3520 cm^{-1} in o-rGO was a flat and broad peak, which strongly shows the presence of hydroxyl moieties such as epoxy, hydroxyl, carbonyl and carboxylic groups. It also confirmed that GO was successfully reduced via thermal reduction because of decrease in intensity that resulted from increased defects in density. There were in addition peaks at 2374 , 2115 , 1701 and 1541 cm^{-1} because of C-O stretching vibrations and OH stretching vibrations. What's more is that several researchers have similarly observed our spectrum in their research work [13-16, 26].

Fig. 2 XRD pattern of GO and o-rGO

Fig. 3 FTIR spectra of (a) GO and (b) o-rGO

3.2 Removal Efficiency

The percentage removal efficiency of Ni^{2+} by the synthesized o-rGO was carefully plotted on the figure 4 below. It can be correctly observed that alkaline pH efficiently removed the adsorbate up to 97.4 % at pH Of 7. In addition, the removal efficiency increased as concentration of the adsorbate increased with maximum removal at 30 mg/L. Correspondingly, much of the adsorbate appears to be adsorbed at 10 mins and curves further towards saturation point. Additionally, the temperature removal efficiency was up to 97.43 % at 303 K (least reaction temperature). Thus, implies that the reaction is endothermic in nature. Consequently, the optimal values of 40 mg/L concentration, contact time of 10 mins, pH of 7, and Temperature of 273 K were within optimum and acceptable experimental values. Subsequently, other researchers have observed high removal efficiencies of 97-99% by reduced graphene oxide [8, 13-14, 17].

Fig. 4 Removal efficiency of Ni^{2+} using o-rGO showing pH, concentration, time and temperature

3.3 Adsorption Isotherm

The graphs for the adsorption isotherms are shown in Fig. 5 and table 1 below that summarizes the calculated

parameters for each adsorption model. The Tempkin isotherm was determined to have the best fitting $R^2 = 0.981$. The Freundlich (solute distribution), Langmuir (monolayer coverage) and Dubinin-radushkevich (DB) had R^2 values of 0.941, 0.921 and 0.866 respectively.

Inspection of the graphs further revealed that Freundlich and Tempkin interaction were negative, while Langmuir and DB had positive adsorptive interaction, which describes a more favorable adsorption isotherm. Furthermore, the absolute intercept value was largest in Tempkin at 126, and lowest in DB at 2.64; hence, adsorption rate was rapid in Tempkin and least in DB.

Fig. 5 o-rGO adsorptive isotherm graphs

Strong van der Waals bonds are formed between the o-rGO adsorbent and Ni^{2+} adsorbate because the β -Tempkin constant is ≥ 20 kJ/mol and the E-energy is greater than 8 kJ/mol. The absolute slopes as shown in the table 1 showed that DB and Freundlich had the least deviation, while Langmuir and Tempkin revealed insignificant errors.

The K_L value of Langmuir was determined to be 1.46; which represent the binding strength. It indicated a weak

binding strength between the Ni^{2+} and the o-rGO; hence a small intercept. In addition the R_L was 0.0168 which is ($0 < R_L < 1$) favorable reaction and agrees with R^2 . In Freundlich, the energy of adsorption “n” was small at 1.18 indicating favorable adsorption mechanisms while $1/n$ was < 1 . The adsorption capacity K_F was calculated to be 1.95 meaning that monolayer adsorption occurred at the surface of the o-rGO [7]. The DB gave the least R^2 fitting and reflected in the small β value at $5.93E^{-5}$. This showed a negligible mean free energy and reflected in small intercept value.

Table 1: Parameters from o-rGO isotherm and kinetic graphs

	SLOPE	Intercept	Correlation coefficient			
Langmuir	10.1	14.8	0.921	qm (mg/g) 0.0676	K_L (1/mg) 1.46	R_L 0.0168
Freundlich	1.18	7.08	0.941	K_F (mg/g) 1.95	n 1.18	1/n 0.847
Tempkin	30.6	126	0.981	β (mol ² kj ⁻²) 30.6	Q_S (mg/g) 61.4	
Dubinin-Radushkevich	$5.93 E^{-5}$	2.64	0.866	B (kj/mol) $5.93 E^{-5}$	K_T 14.0	
Pseudo 1st Order	-0.0881	2.62	0.888	Q_e (exp) 0.418	K₁ (g/mg/min) 0.203	Q_e (cal)(mg/g) 0.816
Pseudo 2nd Order	0.00627	1.082	0.483	H (mg/g/min) 0.927	K₂ 3.62	Q_e (cal)(mg/g) 160
Elovich	7.95	-6.06	0.846	β (g/min) 0.126	α (mg g/min) 2.72	1/β 7.95
Intra-Particle Diffusion	5.50	-6.99	0.962	K_{id} (mg/g/min) 5.50	C (mg/g) -6.99	

3.4 Adsorptive Kinetics

Adsorption studies with contact time constraints have continued to throw more light into reaction mechanisms and pathways especially when applied to study pseudo 1st and 2nd order, Elovich and Intra-particle diffusion. The plotted graphs are shown in Fig. 6 below with conjecture of pseudo 2nd order, and linearity of intra-particle diffusion by inspection. At table 1, intra-particle diffusion showed the best R^2 fitting at 0.946, while pseudo 2nd order had the least correlation coefficient and least described the adsorption process.

The absolute values of the slope and intercept in the Elovich and Intra particle diffusion were significantly bigger than both pseudo 1st and 2nd order. The $q_{e(cal)}$ in pseudo 1st order was more than $q_{e(exp)}$. Consequently, concentration of absorbed Ni^{2+} was considerably smaller in experiment than in theory. At K_1 value of 0.203 (g/mg/min) confirmed a smaller adsorption rate with respect to time.

The pseudo 2nd order graph established no reasonable linear correlation. However, the other constants such as H (mg/g/min) showing initial adsorption rates was very small while the value of K_2 was at 3.62, though showing a faster reaction kinetics but does not agree with initial adsorption rates. Thus, it can be deduced that pseudo 2nd order kinetics were unable to interpret the adsorption process due to weak binding strength. This weak binding

strength was in agreement with K_L value of Langmuir at 1.46, which indicated a low binding constant.

However, a previously published study on reduced graphene oxide for dye removal reported different kinetic results, and may be due to different forms of adsorption interaction mechanism from dyes and Ni^{2+} [27].

Fig. 6 o-rGO adsorptive kinetic graphs

The values of α and β constants in Elovich were 2.72 and 0.126 which showed initial adsorption and desorption constants depicted a non-spontaneous adsorption process. In addition, $1/\beta$ value was determined to be 7.95; and suggested that few adsorptive sites were present for Ni^{2+} adsorption. The “C” constant of intra-particle diffusion was very negligible, and in consequence, a very low-layered thickness. K_{id} at 5.50 was greater than 1 and did not affect the rate constant, thus a higher correlation coefficient value. Since the “C” constant was less than 0 and K_{id} greater than 1, and the linear fitting passed through the origin; it means intra-particle diffusion was the rate-determining step; hence the adsorption of Ni^{2+} is better described by intra-particle diffusion.

3.5 Thermodynamic Study

The thermodynamic constants were evaluated using Van't Hoff's equation and Gibbs free energy equation. The

calculated parameters are shown in table 2. Calculated change in ΔG° value was all positive and indicated a non-spontaneous reaction. The ΔG° values decreased as the temperature increased, which implies that the reaction would favorably occur at lower temperatures. Moreover, since ΔG° is $> 0 < 3$; indicated a non-physio-sorption mechanism. The values of change in ΔH° and change in ΔS° were determined from the slope and intercept of plot $\ln K_c$ against $1/T$. The enthalpy change was 2.78 kJ/mol, which also point towards the endothermic process of the adsorption. The entropy value was at -0.948 kJ/mol and showed the enthalpy effect will cause the reaction to be effective at lower temperature. This result is in agreement with effect of temperature as earlier discussed in section 3.2. In addition, the decrease of adsorption at more elevated temperature confirms the destruction of active binding sites in the reduced o-rGO as well as the weakening of the attractive force between the o-rGO and Ni^{2+}

Table 2: Thermodynamic parameters for adsorption of Ni^{2+} onto o-rGO

Adsorbent	Adsorbate	ΔS° (j/mol/K)	ΔH° (KJ/mol)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)		
				303	315	328
O-rGO	Ni^{2+}	-0.948	2.78	1.01	1.47	2.76

4. Conclusion

This study shows that orange extract reduced graphene oxide (o-rGO) is a suitable material for removal of Ni^{2+} from aqueous solution. The research also confirms that thermal reduction of graphene oxide to reduced graphene oxide was successful. SEM images, wavelength shift in FTIR spectrum, and increase in crystallite size in X-ray diffraction also showed a successful characterization. The o-rGO sheets were closely packed and suggested potential properties of the reduced graphene oxide for materials application such as supercapacitors, sensors and photocatalytic applications. Some research challenges included absence of transmission electron microscope and atomic force microscopy that will fine-tune the research data [1, 28]. In summary Tempkin isotherm model best described the mechanism with regression coefficient of 0.981; while Intra-particle diffusion had the best adsorption kinetic model with regression coefficient of 0.946 and represents the rate-determining step. On the other hand, thermodynamics showed an endothermic process and non-spontaneous reaction, likewise removal efficiencies of 97 % was achieved.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists.

Acknowledgments

The authors are very grateful for the laboratory support received from FUTO chemistry staff

References

1. A.T Smith, A.M La Chance, S. Zeng, B. Liu, and L. Sun, *Nano Mater. Sci.* 1(1), 31-47 (2019) [doi:10.1016/j.nanoms.2019.02.004].

2. X.J. Lee, B.Y.Z. Hiew, K.C. Lai, L.Y. Lee, S. Gan, T.G. Suchithra and R. Sean, *J. Taiwan Inst. Chem. Eng.* 98, 163-180 (2019) [doi: 10.1016/j.jtice.2018.10.028].
3. I. Gómez, E. Mejía, and R. Cabanzo, *Revista Colombiana de Mater.* 5 (2014) 177-184.
4. D. Mercano, D. Kosynkin, J. Berlin, A. Sinitskii, Z. Sun, and S. Slesarev, *ACS NANO.* 12, 2078-2078 (2018) [doi: 10.1021/nn1006368].
5. N.A. Udoka, E.C. Kenechukwu, *Phy Chem Res.* 7(2), 295-307 (2019) [doi: 10.22036/pcr.2018.148061.1538].
6. A.U. Nkwoada, K.D. Okoli, I.O. Ekeanyanwu, *J. App Chem. Sci. Int.* 7(1), 64-70 (2016).
7. R. Mallampati, L. Xuanjun, A. Adin, and S. Valiyaveetti, *ACS Sust Chem. Eng.* 3(6), 1117-1124 (2015) [doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.5b00207].
8. S. Songsaeng, P. Thamyongkit, S. Poompradub, *J. Adv.Res.* 20, 79-89 (2019) [doi: 10.1016/j.jare.2019.05.007].
9. S. Chinnasamy, J. Ramasamy, B. Partha, R. Shrestha, A. Katsuhiko, K.S. Lok, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan.*, 90 (8) (2017) 955-962. [doi:10.1246/bcsj.20170092].
10. R. Appan, P. Arneish, B. Suddhasatwa, K.J Sandeep, *J. Nanopart Res.* 20 (70), 1-17 (2018).
11. S. Khan, A. Farooqi, A. Danish and A. Zeb, *Int. J. Recent Res and App. Sci.* 16(2) (2013) 297-306.
12. X. Guo, S. Liang, Q. Tian, *Adv. Mater. Res.* 236(238), 237-240 (2011) [10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.236-238.237].
13. L. Gan, B. Li, Y. Chen, B. Yu, Z. Chen. *Chemosphere.* 219, 148-154 (2018) [doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.11.181].
14. S. Ahmad, A. Ahmad, S. Khan, S. Ahmad, I. Khan, S. Zada, P.Fu, *J. Indust. Eng. Chem.* 72, 117-124 (2019) [doi:10.1016/j.jiec.2018.12.009].
15. A. Raja, P. Rajasekaran, K. Selvakumar, M. Arivanandhan, S.A. Bahadur, M. Swaminathan, *Optiks.* 190 (2019) 21-27 [doi:10.1016/j.ijleo.2019.05.052]
16. P. Zhang, Z. Li, S. Zhang and G. Shao, *Energy Environ Mater.* 1, 5-12 (2018) [doi: 10.1002/eem2.12001].
17. K.R. Upadhyay, N. Soin, G. Bhattacharya, S. Saha, A. Barman, and S.S Roy, *Mater. Lett.* 160, 355-358 (2015) [doi:10.1016/j.matlet.2015.07.144].
18. N. Mahato, K. Sharma, M. Sinha, E.R. Baral, R. Koteswararao, A. Dhyani, M.H. Cho, S. Choa, *J. Adv. Res.* 23, 61-82 (2020) [doi: 10.1016/j.jare.2020.01.007].
19. S.A.X Stango, U. Vijayalakshmi, *J. Asian. Ceram. Soc.* 6(1), 20-29 (2018) [doi:10.1080/21870764.2018.1439608].
20. L.A. Romero-Cano, H. García-Rosero, L.V. Gonzalez-Gutierrez, L.A. Baldenegro-Pérez, F. Carrasco-Marín, *J. Clenaner. Prod.*, 162, (2017) 195-204.
21. J. Song, X. Wang, C. Chang, *J. Nanomater.*, Article ID 276143 (2014) 1-6. [doi:10.1155/2014/276143]
22. F. Khurshid, M. Jeyavelan, M. Hudson and S. Nagarajan, *Royal Soc. Open Sci.* 6(2), 1-13 (2019) [doi:10.1098/rsos.181764].
23. S. Sagadevan, A.R. Marlinda, M.R. Johan, A. Umar, H. Foyad, O.Y. Alothman, U. Khaled, M.S. Aktar, M.M. Shahid, *J. Coll Intf Sci.*, 558 (2020) 68-77.
24. K. Hareesh, R.P. Joshi, S. Dahiwalé, V.N. Bhoraskar, S. Dhole, *Vacuum.*, 124, 40-45 (2016) [doi:10.1016/j.vacuum.2015.11.011].
25. V.C. Saha, M.A. Sabuj, P. Shams, S. Rahman, M.R, Qadir, M.R, Islam, F. Gulshan. IOP Conf. Series: Mater. Sci. Eng. 438 (2018) 1-8 [doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1706/1/012028].
26. I. Gomez, E. Mejia and R. Cabanzo, *Revista Colombiana de Mater.* 5, 177-184 (2017).
27. L. Gan, B. Li, Y. Chen, B. Yu, Z. Chen, *Chemosphere.* 219, 148-154. (2019) [10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.11.181]
28. A.U. Nkwoada, C.M. Amakom and E.E. Oguzie, *Asian J. Phy. Chem. Sci.* 5(2), 1-19 (2018) [doi:10.9734/AJOPACS/2018/39683]